

Evaluation of Tumor Marker Serum Carbohydrate Antigen 19-9 Level in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients in Indian Population**Hiranmoy Karmakar^{1*}, Sarla Mahawar², Deepa Thadani³, Kamlesh Tanwani⁴, Ajay Jain⁵**¹Resident (Jr-3), Department of Biochemistry, JLN Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India²Senior Professor, Department of Biochemistry, JLN Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India³Senior Professor and Head, Department of Biochemistry, JLN Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, JLN Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, JLN Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Hiranmoy Karmakar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a worldwide health problem, affecting millions of people. Causes of chronic kidney disease include diabetes, high blood pressure, glomerulonephritis, polycystic kidney disease, lupus, and other forms of cardiovascular diseases. Serum Carbohydrate Antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9) is a tumor marker for conditions such as benign ovarian tumors, malignancies of pancreas, colorectum, lung, chronic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, diseases of bile duct but its level is also high in chronic renal disorder. Our study was aimed to assess and compare the status of serum CA 19-9 level in chronic kidney disease subjects and healthy controls.

Materials and Methods: The present study is a case-control study, conducted on 220 CKD patients. Cases were selected from the Medical ward of Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Associated Group of Hospitals, Ajmer. Age and sex-matched healthy controls (n = 100) were selected from MOPD. The present study is approved by Institutional Ethical Committee. All samples were collected under aseptic conditions from the antecubital vein.

Results: The mean activity of Serum CA 19-9 was significantly higher in CKD subjects as compared to healthy controls ($p < 0.0001$). The observations of this study also revealed that 150 out of 220 CKD patients have higher serum CA 19-9 levels (>35 U/mL). Positive Pearson correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 was found ($r = 0.76$).

Conclusion: Serum CA 19-9 can be used as a biomarker for the early detection of CKD in the general population to prevent the morbidity and mortality which are associated with CKD. If CKD is detected early and managed appropriately the deterioration in kidney functions can be slowed and the risk of cardiovascular diseases in renal patients can be reduced.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease (CKD), Carbohydrate Antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9), End-stage renal disease (ESRD), Glomerular filtration rate (GFR), Chronic renal failure (CRF).

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a worldwide health problem, affecting millions of people. CKD is defined as kidney damage or glomerular filtration rate (GFR) <60 mL/min/1.73 m² for 3 months or more, irrespective of cause. [1] CKD represents a progressive, irreversible decline in GFR. CKD is a type of kidney disease in which there is a gradual loss of kidney function over a period of months to years. Causes of chronic kidney disease includes diabetes, high blood pressure, glomerulonephritis, and polycystic kidney disease. Loss of renal function is common in renal failure, irrespective of the underlying cause of the kidney disease.

Tumor markers are bio-chemical substances that result as normal endogenous products that are produced at a greater rate in cancer cells or are the products of newly switched on genes that remained quiescent in the normal cells. [2] Tumor markers are used for clinical purposes such as screening, early detection, diagnostic confirmation, prognosis and prediction of therapeutic response, and monitoring disease and recurrence. [3]

CA 19-9 also known as Sialyl-Lewis, is a 210 KD tumor-associated glycoprotein antigen present as carbohydrate determinant on glycolipid and glycoprotein. [4] It is a tetrasaccharide which is usually attached to O-glycans on the surface of cells. Ab-

normal serum concentration of CA 19-9 is found in a spectrum of conditions such as benign ovarian tumors, malignancies of pancreas, colorectum, lung, chronic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, diseases of bile duct and also in CKD. CA 19-9 is reported to be cleared through kidneys and hence, reduction in GFR and reduced tubular activity may affect the clearance of CA 19-9. [5] Tumor marker such as the tumor associated antigen CA 19-9, is reported to be increased in CKD, even in the absence of malignancy [6]. CA 19-9 is filtered by glomerulus and almost completely reabsorbed and metabolised by renal tubules. In 99.6% of healthy adults, serum CA 19-9 levels are lower than 37 U/mL. Value less than 100 U/mL is considered as grey zone values in which malignant and benign diseases may overlap. Malignant tumors in values above 100 U/mL may be observed. [7]

Studies found that CA 19-9 could be a marker for kidney injury related to urinary obstruction in their research on patients with hydronephrosis. [8,9] In another study conducted on people with urolithiasis and hydronephrosis before and after a procedure called transurethral lithotripsy the affected group had a significant elevation before the operation, which decreased in the following measurements. [10] Serum CA 19-9 levels returned to the normal range by treating the underlying lesions involving the kidney by nephrectomy, complete removal of stones, nephrostomy. The serum CA 19-9 has prognostic importance in chronic renal disorder. Increasing levels signal a higher risk of ESRD mortality.

Serum urea and serum creatinine are widely accepted as the most common parameters to assess renal functions. The prevalence of CKD in general population was 16% in India. [11] If CKD is detected early and managed appropriately the deterioration in kidney functions can be slowed and the risk of cardiovascular diseases in renal patients can be reduced. Our study was aimed to assess and compare the status of serum CA 19-9 in chronic kidney disease patients and healthy controls.

Materials and Methodology

The present study is a case-control study. For the 95% confidence level, desired sample size was calculated using the formula $n = (p)(q)(z/d)^2$. The study was conducted on 220 chronic kidney disease patients. Patients were diagnosed as chronic kidney disease on the basis of clinical history, physical examination, serum urea and serum creatinine level. Cases were selected from the medical ward of Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Associated Group of Hospital, Ajmer. Age and sex-matched healthy controls (n=100) were selected from Medicine OPD of Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical

College and Associated Group of Hospital, Ajmer. The results of patients were compared with healthy controls (n=100).

For the control group: Age and sex-matched healthy individuals were included.

Inclusion criteria for the study group: Established cases of chronic kidney disease between age 30-60 years were taken.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Acute kidney injury, acute infection, acute myocardial infarction, active liver disease or liver dysfunction, hematological and malignant overt diseases.
2. Cases associated with other inflammatory diseases such as cancer or autoimmunity.
3. Kidney transplant patients.
4. Pregnant and lactating women.
5. Lack of compliance with the protocol.
6. Patients who were unwilling to participate in the study were excluded.

Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast (12-14hrs) under aseptic conditions from all the study participants. All samples were centrifuged and analysed for serum urea, serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9. Serum urea was measured by Berthelot enzymatic colorimetric method. [12] Serum creatinine was measured by Jaffe's colorimetric kinetic method. [13] Serum CA 19-9 was measured by Chemiluminescence Immunoassay method. [14]

Statistical Analysis

All data were analysed by SPSS Version 27.0. $P < 0.0001$ was considered highly significant. Pearson correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 was performed.

Results

A total of 320 subjects were studied. The results are summarized in Tables and Figures. The Table-1, Figure-1 show the Mean \pm SD of serum urea, serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9. The Table-1, Figure- 1, serum urea (179.01 ± 33.39 v/s 23.36 ± 6.75) mg/dl, serum creatinine (7.37 ± 2.54 v/s 0.86 ± 0.52) mg/dl and serum CA 19-9 (55.32 ± 29.37 v/s 6.23 ± 4.45) U/mL in chronic kidney disease subjects compared to healthy controls were highly significantly ($P < 0.0001$). 150 out of 220 chronic kidney disease patients have higher serum CA 19-9 levels (> 35 U/mL). The Table-2, Figure- 2 show the serum CA 19-9 level in chronic kidney disease subjects. Figure 3 shows positive correlation ($r = 0.76$) between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 in CKD subjects.

Table 1: Biochemical Parameters of Healthy Control Subjects v/s Chronic Kidney Disease Subjects

Biochemical Parameters	Healthy Controls Subjects (n = 100) (Mean ± SD)	CKD subjects (n= 220) (Mean ± SD)	P VALUE
1. Serum urea (mg/dL)	23.36 ± 6.75	179.01 ± 33.39	P<0.0001*
2. Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	0.86 ± 0.52	7.37 ± 2.54	P<0.0001*
3. Serum CA 19-9 (U/mL)	6.23 ± 4.45	53.32 ± 29.37	P<0.0001*

Figure 1: Comparison of Biochemical Parameters of Healthy Control Subjects V/S Chronic Kidney Disease Subjects

Table 2: Serum CA 19-9 levels in Chronic Kidney Disease Subjects

Serum CA 19-9 Level (U/mL)	% Of Chronic Kidney Disease Subjects
< 35.0	32 %
35.1 – 70.0	35 %
70.1 – 105.0	27 %
105.1 – 140.0	6 %

Figure 2: Serum CA 19-9 levels in Chronic Kidney Disease Subjects

Table 3. Comparison of our observations of tumor markers in chronic kidney disease with other studies

Tumor marker	Engin H et al [15]	Arik N et al [16]	Rani BS et al [17]	Present Study
Serum CA 19-9 (U/mL)	↑	↑	↑	↑

↑: Increase

Figure 3: Pearson correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 in CKD cases.

Discussion

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a worldwide health problem, affecting millions of people. Causes of chronic kidney disease include diabetes, high blood pressure, glomerulonephritis and polycystic kidney disease. Other health conditions that may lead to CKD are obesity, high cholesterol, a family history of the disease kidney disease, lupus and other forms of cardiovascular diseases.

In the present study we have observed the level of serum CA 19-9 was elevated in chronic kidney disease patients as compared to the healthy subjects (controls). Our findings are in agreement with Engin H et al, Arik N et al, Rani BS et al who found that the mean activity of serum CA 19-9 was significantly higher in chronic kidney disease patients compared to the healthy subjects (Table 3). Significantly higher levels of serum CA 19-9 ($P < 0.0001$) with a 8.8-fold increase in CKD cases when compared with controls was observed.

Abnormal serum concentration of CA 19-9 is found in a spectrum of conditions such as malignancies of pancreas, colorectum, lung, chronic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, diseases of bile duct, benign ovarian tumors, and also in CKD. CA 19-9 is excreted by the kidney. Thus patients with end stage renal disease have elevated levels of serum CA 19-9. Serum CA 19-9 are increased in patients with renal insufficiency due to decreased excretion of the glycolipid. The levels are not as high as malignancies. Serum CA 19-9 is filtered by glomerulus and almost com-

pletely reabsorbed and metabolised by renal tubules. Reduced clearance of CA 19-9 from the circulation can occur with chronic renal failure. The observations of this study also revealed that 150 out of 220 chronic kidney disease patients have higher serum CA 19-9 levels (>35 U/mL). Positive Pearson correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 was found ($r = 0.76$).

Conclusion

It is important to determine the effect of CKD on the levels of serum CA 19-9 in blood, to avoid misinterpretation of tumor markers in arriving at the diagnosis of malignancy in CKD patients. Other studies correlating serum CA 19-9 in CKD patients were not well documented and showed positive as well as negative correlation. In the present study an attempt was made to compare the levels of serum CA 19-9 in CKD patients with healthy controls and to find out the correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 in CKD patients. This study allowed establishing that serum CA 19-9 is a potential alternative indicator of renal functions and also predicted the susceptibility of individuals for developing CKD. Moreover, it also assessed reliability, sensitivity and high diagnostic accuracy of parameters between healthy individuals and CKD patients.

Serum CA 19-9 was found to be elevated in chronic kidney disease patients. The observations of this study has also revealed that 150 out of 220 chronic kidney disease patients have higher serum

CA 19-9 levels (>35 U/mL). Positive Pearson correlation between serum creatinine and serum CA 19-9 was found ($r=0.76$). Serum CA 19-9 can be used as a biomarker for the early detection of chronic kidney disease in the general population to prevent the morbidity and mortality which are associated with chronic kidney disease.

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